

**Studies on the Dependence of Optical Rotatory Power on
Chemical Constitution. Part XIV. Stereoisomeric
Aminomethylenecamphors, Iminomethylene-
camphors and their Derivatives.**

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For a comparative study of the effect of substitution on rotatory power of the derivatives of aminomethylenecamphor and iminomethylenecamphor, some of which have been already described (Singh and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 771; 1931, 8, 181; Singh, Bhaduri and Barat, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 345), it is necessary to know the rotation constants of the parent compounds. With this object in view, the rotatory dispersion of stereoisomeric aminomethylenecamphors and iminomethylenecamphors have been described in the present paper.

The *laevo* and *racemic* isomerides of aminomethylenecamphors are new substances and were prepared in the usual way (*vide*, Experimental).

Benzylaminomethylenecamphors were prepared in the usual way by the condensation of benzylamine with oxymethylenecamphor (*d, l, dl*).

Iminomethylene-*d*-camphor was also prepared according to the method of Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*Annalen*, 1894, 281, 359), but the yield was very poor. It was, however, obtained in a better yield by the condensation of aminomethylene-*d*-camphor with oxymethylene-*d*-camphor (*vide*, Experimental). The *laevo*, *racemic* and the *meso* isomerides were prepared in the same way.

*The Effect of Chemical Constitution and the Nature of Solvent
on the Rotatory Power.*

(i) On comparing the structural formulae and specific rotatory power of aminomethylenecamphor (I), anilinomethylenecamphor

(II), and benzylaminomethylenecamphor (III), the following conclusions may be drawn:—

Structural formula.	$[\alpha]_{D}^{35}$ H _g ⁵⁴⁶¹ (in chloroform).
I. R=CH·NH ₂	+350.0°
II. R=CH·NH·C ₆ H ₅	424.6
III. R=CH·NH·CH·C ₆ H ₅	339.9
IV. R=CH·NH·CH=R	678.4

The phenyl group in (II) which is not in conjugation with the ethenoid and carbonyl groups has very little effect in increasing the rotatory power of the parent compound (I); and its further removal from the asymmetric centre by the interposition of the methylene group as in (III) lowers the rotation only to a slight extent (II→III).

(ii) The specific rotatory power of iminomethylenecamphor (IV), is nearly twice that of aminomethylenecamphor (I); this great increase in specific rotatory power can be accounted for by depicting the double symmetric tautomeric formula (V) for this compound, in which the conjugation between ethenoid, azethenoid and carbonyl groups is complete.

The compound does not, however, exhibit the expected fluorescence.

(iii) It is found that the order of decreasing rotatory power is ethyl alcohol > methyl alcohol > pyridine > acetone > chloroform > benzene, for aminomethylene-, and iminomethylenecamphors. The sequence of the dielectric constants of the solvents is also the same, except that the position of ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol is reversed. The same is the case with pyridine and acetone in the above mentioned sequence. For iminomethylenecamphor, however,

the values of specific rotatory power in pyridine and acetone (Tables VIII and IX) become identical for Li_{6104} and beyond this towards the red end of the spectrum e.g., Li_{6708} , that in acetone is greater than that for pyridine, whereas towards the violet region the order is reversed. For benzylaminomethylenecamphor, the order of decreasing rotatory power agrees exactly with the sequence of the dielectric constants of the solvents, viz., methyl alcohol > ethyl alcohol > acetone > pyridine > chloroform > benzene.

The Nature of Rotatory Dispersion.

Optically active aminomethylenecamphors and iminomethylene-camphors, like their derivatives, obey the one-term simple dispersion formula of Drude, viz., $[\alpha] = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$. On plotting $\frac{1}{[\alpha]}$ against λ^2 in each case a straight line is obtained. In the tables of rotatory dispersion (I—XI), a more exact test of the formula is provided by numerical calculations.

The value of the hypothetical absorption band in the ultra-violet region of the spectrum, λ_0 is lower for aminomethylenecamphor than that for iminomethylenecamphor, which shows that the absorption band is shifted towards the visible side of the spectrum in the case of the latter compound.

The Physical Identity of Isomers.

The values of rotatory power of *d* and *l* forms in different solvents (Tables I—XII) are identical within limits of experimental error. Out of 97 observations which are now recorded, in as many as 81 cases, the differences in the numerical value of the rotatory power of the opposite isomers correspond to a difference of less than 0.01° in the observed angle of rotation, and in other 15 cases, the corresponding angle lies between 0.01° to 0.02° , which is the limit of experimental error allowable in such measurements. Only in the remaining solitary case of iminomethylenecamphor in ethyl alcohol for Cd_{4800} (Table X), the difference corresponds to between 0.02° and 0.03° in the observed angle of rotation. This is, however, of the nature of casual experimental error. This, therefore, further supports Pasteur's principle of molecular dissymmetry, according to which the two forms, *dextro* and *laevo*, must possess equal and opposite rotatory power.

The melting point of the *racemic* form of aminomethylene-camphor is higher than that of the optically active isomers. This form is a true *dl*-compound, at least, in the solid state.

Examples of racemic forms having identical melting points with those of the active forms are very rare. A few examples have already been cited in a previous communication (Singh and Bhaduri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 623). In the present paper we record one more similar instance, *viz.*, iminomethylenecamphor (m. p. 216-18°).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Aminomethylene-d-camphor (I) was prepared in the same way as that of Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*loc. cit.*) and has the same crystalline form (shining white prisms), but melts at 157°, instead of 163-64°, which agrees with that observed by Rupe (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1920, 3, 50). (Found: C, 73.57; H, 9.73; N, 8.01. $C_{11}H_{17}ON$ requires C, 73.74; H, 9.50; N, 7.82 per cent.). The *l*-variety, m. p. 157°. (Found: N, 7.94). The *dl*-variety, m. p. 163-64°. (Found: N, 8.00).

Iminomethylene-d-camphor.—Aminomethylene-*d*-camphor (2.5 g.) dissolved in glacial acetic acid, was added to oxymethylene-*d*-camphor (2.5 g.) dissolved in methyl alcohol, and diluted with water when a precipitate separated at once. It was washed with dilute caustic soda solution and then with water and crystallised out of methyl alcohol as long needles, m. p. 216-18°, yield 80 p. c. It is freely soluble in chloroform and pyridine; less so in acetone and ethyl alcohol and difficultly soluble in methyl alcohol and benzene. (Found: C, 77.29; H, 9.15. $C_{22}H_{31}O_2N$ requires C, 77.42; H, 9.09; N, 4.11 per cent.). The *l*-variety, m. p. 216-18°. (Found: N, 4.20). The *dl*-variety, m. p. 216-18°. (Found: N, 4.29).

Iminomethylene-*d*-camphor was also prepared by the method of Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*loc. cit.*) by the action of strong hydrochloric acid on aminomethylene-*d*-camphor. The yield is, however, very poor, but the melting point is the same as by the above mentioned method. The mixed melting point of the product prepared by the two methods was also 216-18°. Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair (*loc. cit.*) give 221-22° as the melting point.

Internally Compensated or meso-Iminomethylenecamphors.—(1) Aminomethylene-*d*-camphor (1 mol.) in glacial acetic acid was added to oxymethylene-*l*-camphor (1 mol.) and the precipitate so obtained was repeatedly crystallised out of dilute methyl alcohol

as white prismatic needles, m. p. 217-18°. (Found: C, 77.25; H, 9.17. $C_{23}H_{31}O_2N$ requires C, 77.42; H, 9.09; N, 4.11 per cent.).

(2) In the same way amidomethylene-*l*-camphor was condensed with oxymethylene-*d*-camphor and white prismatic needles melting at 217-18° were obtained. (Found: N, 4.23).

On polarimetric examination both the compounds were found to be inactive.

The condensed product of oxymethylenecamphor with methylamine (obtained in the usual way) was an oil which refused to solidify.

Benzylaminomethylene-d-camphor (III).—Oxymethylene-*d*-camphor was condensed in the usual way with benzylamine hydrochloride in presence of a little fused sodium acetate and the oil obtained on dilution with water was left overnight when it solidified. It was crystallised out of dilute methyl alcohol (charcoal) as fine white needles, m. p. 89-91°. It is freely soluble in all the ordinary organic media. (Found: C, 80.18; H, 8.70; N, 5.41. $C_{18}H_{23}ON$ requires C, 80.30; H, 8.55; N, 5.21 per cent.). The solutions of the substance in different solvents (except in ethyl alcohol, Table XI) exhibited rapid mutarotation and turned scarlet in a short time; hence their rotatory dispersion could not be studied for more than two lines (Table XII). The *l*-form, m.p. 89-91°. (Found: N, 5.36). The *dl*-form, m.p. 84-85°. (Found: N, 5.40).

The rotatory power determinations were made in a 2-dcm jacketed tube at 35°. The value of λ_0 , calculated from the dispersion formula, is given in the tables and is expressed as μ or 10^{-4} cm.

TABLE I.
Aminomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{68.33}{\lambda^2 - 0.1025} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3202.$$

Dextro			Line.	calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	Laevo		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o	o-c.			o-c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.4000	+535.0°	+0.3°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	±534.7°	-1.3°	-533.5°	0.4040
	436.3	-1.1	Cd ₅₀₈₆	437.4	+0.7	438.1	
	403.8	-1.0	Ag ₅₂₀₉	404.8	± 0	404.8	
	350.0	+0.9	Hg ₅₄₆₁	349.1	-0.2	348.9	
	296.3	+1.2	Hg ₅₇₃₀	295.1	+0.6	295.7	
	278.8	-0.5	Na ₅₈₉₃	279.3	-0.1	279.2	
	253.8	+0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	253.0	+0.7	253.7	
	218.8	-0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₃	219.0	+0.1	219.1	
	196.3	-0.3	Li ₆₇₀₃	196.6	-1.0	195.6	

The solution exhibited slight mutarotation; the initial values $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg6461}} = 350.0^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg5780}} = 296.3^\circ$ changing to 345.0° and 290.0° respectively in course of 20 hours.

TABLE II.

Aminomethylenecamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{72.04}{\lambda^2 - 0.0944} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3072.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.			o'-c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'.	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.4036	+438.6°	+0.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±438.5°	-1.0°	-437.5°	0.4000
	406.5	-0.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	407.3	+0.2	407.5	
	354.3	+0.8	Hg ₆₄₆₁	353.5	+0.3	353.8	
	301.1	+0.6	Hg ₅₇₈₀	300.5	-0.5	300.0	
	283.7	-1.3	Na ₅₈₉₃	285.0	± 0	285.0	
	259.0	+0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	258.9	-0.1	258.8	
	224.3	-0.8	Cd ₆₄₃₈	225.1	-0.1	225.0	
	202.0	-0.6	Li ₆₇₀₈	202.6	-0.1	202.5	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE III.

Aminomethylenecamphor in Methyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{75.33}{\lambda^2 - 0.1919} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3192.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.			o'-c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'.	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.4004	+479.6°	+1.1°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±478.5°	-0.5°	-478.0°	0.4048
	442.1	-0.8	Ag ₅₂₀₉	442.9	+0.5	443.4	
	383.4	+1.2	Hg ₆₄₆₁	382.2	-0.5	381.7	
	323.4	+0.3	Hg ₅₇₈₀	323.1	+0.5	323.6	
	304.7	-1.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	305.8	-0.7	305.1	
	277.3	+0.2	Li ₆₁₀₄	277.1	+0.8	277.9	
	239.8	-0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	240.0	-0.4	239.6	
	214.9	-0.6	Li ₆₇₀₈	215.5	+0.7	216.2	

The solution exhibited mutarotation; the initial values $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg6461}} = 383.4^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg5780}} = 323.4^\circ$ changing to 368.4° and 308.4° respectively in course of 20 hours.

TABLE IV.

Aminomethylenecamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{77.13}{\lambda^2 - 0.1006}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3172.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	<i>Laevo</i>			
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o.c.		calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	o'.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'.	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.3996	+486.7°	-1.2°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±487.9°	+0.9°	-488.8°	0.4040
	451.7	-0.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	451.9	-0.1	451.8	
	390.3	±0	Hg ₅₄₆₁	390.3	-0.4	399.9	
	330.4	+0.1	Hg ₅₇₈₀	330.3	+0.3	330.6	
	312.7	-0.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	312.8	+0.3	313.1	
	284.2	+0.7	Li ₆₁₀₄	283.5	-0.1	283.4	
	246.5	+0.8	Cd ₆₄₃₈	245.7	-0.6	245.1	
	220.3	-0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	220.7	+0.8	221.5	

The solution exhibited mutarotation; the initial values $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5461}} = 390.3^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5780}} = 330.4^\circ$ changing to 367.9° and 306.6° respectively in course of 20 hours.

TABLE V.

Aminomethylenecamphor in Benzene.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{74.90}{\lambda^2 - 0.0816}; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.2857.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	<i>Laevo</i>			
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o.c.		calc. $[\alpha]$ o.	o'.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'.	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.3996	+422.3°	-0.2°	Cd ₅₀₈₆	±423.0°	+1.0°	-424.0°	0.4080
	394.2	-0.6	Ag ₅₂₀₉	394.8	-0.1	394.7	
	346.6	+0.7	Hg ₅₄₆₁	345.9	-0.3	345.6	
	297.7	+1.1	Hg ₅₇₈₀	296.6	±0	296.6	
	281.5	-0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	281.9	±0	281.9	
	257.8	+0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	257.4	-0.1	257.3	
	225.2	+0.2	Cd ₆₄₃₈	225.0	+0.5	225.5	
	202.7	-0.6	Li ₆₇₀₈	208.3	+0.2	203.5	

The solution exhibited mutarotation; the initial values $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5461}} = 346.6^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5780}} = 297.7^\circ$ changing to 336.6° and 287.7° respectively in course of 8 hours.

TABLE VI.

Aminomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{79.94}{\lambda^2 - 0.0893} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.1120.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	calc. $[\alpha]$ o.	<i>Laevo</i>		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.			o'-c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'	conc. g/100 c.c.
3.0016	+471.7*	-0.1*	Cd ₅₀₈₆	$\pm 471.8^\circ$	+0.2*	-472.0*	3.0024
	438.9	-0.2	Ag ₅₂₀₉	439.1	-0.3	438.8	
	382.4	-0.1	Hg ₅₄₆₁	382.5	± 0	382.5	
	326.15	-0.35	Hg ₅₇₈₀	326.5	-0.3	326.2	
	309.9	+0.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	309.8	-0.3	309.5	
	282.1	± 0	Li ₆₁₀₄	282.1	+0.1	282.2	
	245.5	-0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	245.6	± 0	245.6	
	221.9	+0.3	Li ₆₇₀₈	221.6	+0.25	221.85	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE VII.

Iminomethylenecamphor in Chloroform.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{124.9}{\lambda^2 - 0.1139} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3375.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	<i>Laevo</i>			
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.		calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	o'-c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.4032	+1072.0*	-1.0*	Cd ₄₈₀₀	$\pm 1073.0^\circ$	-0.5*	-1072.5*	0.4000
	862.0	-0.6	Cd ₅₀₈₆	862.6	-0.1	862.5	
	792.5	-1.1	Ag ₅₂₀₉	793.6	+0.2	793.8	
	678.4	+0.6	Hg ₅₄₆₁	677.8	-0.3	677.5	
	568.1	± 0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	567.3	+0.2	567.5	
	535.8	+0.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	535.2	-0.2	535.0	
	482.4	-0.4	Li ₆₁₀₄	482.8	+1.0	483.8	
	415.5	± 0	Cd ₆₄₃₈	415.5	+0.8	416.3	
	372.1	+0.4	Li ₆₇₀₈	371.7	-0.4	371.3	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE VIII.

Iminomethylenecamphor in Pyridine.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{122.4}{\lambda^2 - 0.1291} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3593.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	calc. [α] c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. [α] o.	o-c.			o'-c.	obs. [α] o'.	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.4000	+1206.3°	-1.7°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	±1208.0	+0.4°	-1208.4°	0.4072
	945.0	+0.5	Cd ₅₀₈₆	944.5	-0.2	944.3	
	861.3	+0.5	Ag ₅₂₀₉	860.8	-1.0	859.8	
	722.5	-1.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	723.8	-0.6	723.2	
	596.3	-0.7	Hg ₅₇₈₀	597.0	+1.0	598.0	
	561.3	+0.4	Na ₅₈₉₃	560.9	+0.4	561.3	
	503.8	+1.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	502.7	-0.4	502.3	
	428.8	-0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	428.9	-0.3	428.6	
	381.3	-0.1	Li ₆₇₀₈	381.4	+0.6	382.0	

The solution did not exhibit mutarotation.

TABLE IX.

Iminomethylenecamphor in Acetone.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{127.4}{\lambda^2 - 0.1194} ; \lambda_0 = 0.3455.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	calc. [α] c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. [α] o.	o-c.			o'-c.	obs. [α] o'.	conc. g/100 c.c.
0.4000	+1146.3°	-1.7°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	±1148.0°	-1.0°	-1147.0°	0.4060
	913.8	-0.5	Cd ₅₀₈₆	914.3	-0.4	913.9	
	838.8	+0.1	Ag ₅₂₀₉	838.7	+0.2	838.9	
	713.7	+1.3	Hg ₅₄₆₁	712.4	-0.4	712.0	
	592.5	-0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	593.3	+0.4	593.7	
	560.0	+1.2	Na ₅₈₉₃	558.3	-0.8	558.0	
	503.8	+0.8	Li ₆₁₀₄	508.0	-0.4	502.6	
	431.3	-0.3	Cd ₆₄₃₈	431.6	+0.7	432.3	
	385.0	-0.2	Li ₆₇₀₈	385.2	+0.3	385.5	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE X.

Iminomethylenecamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{132.4}{\lambda^2 - 0.1245} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3528.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.			o'-c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'. g/100 c.c.	conc.
0.3992	+1252.6°	+1.6°	Cd ₄₈₀₀	±1251.0°	-1.0°	-1250.0°	0.4040
	986.0	-0.7	Cd ₅₀₈₆	986.7	+0.9	987.6	
	901.8	-0.8	Ag ₅₃₀₉	902.6	+0.8	903.4	
	761.7	-0.7	Hg ₅₄₆₁	762.4	+0.1	62.5	
	632.6	+0.8	Hg ₅₇₈₀	631.8	-0.5	631.3	
	593.8	-0.6	Na ₅₈₉₃	594.4	-0.4	594.0	
	533.6	-0.1	Li ₆₁₀₄	533.7	-0.2	533.5	
	457.1	+0.1	Cd ₆₄₃₈	456.7	+0.1	456.8	
	407.1	+0.3	Li ₆₇₀₅	406.8	+0.5	407.3	

The solution did not exhibit any mutarotation.

TABLE XI.

Benzylaminomethylenecamphor in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$[\alpha] = \pm \frac{65.77}{\lambda^2 - 0.1112} ; \quad \lambda_0 = 0.3335.$$

<i>Dextro</i>			Line.	calc. $[\alpha]$ c.	<i>Laevo</i>		
conc. g/100 c.c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o.	o-c.			o'-c.	obs. $[\alpha]$ o'. g/100 c.c.	conc.
0.4020	+352.0°	+0.3°	Hg ₅₄₆₁	±351.7°	-0.1°	-351.6°	0.4052
	294.8	-0.2	Hg ₅₇₈₀	295.0	-0.1	294.9	
	278.7	+0.1	Na ₅₈₉₃	278.6	+0.3	278.9	
	251.3	-0.3	Li ₆₁₀₄	251.6	+0.1	251.7	
	217.7	+0.7	Cd ₆₄₃₈	217.0	+0.3	217.2	
	193.1	-1.0	Li ₆₇₀₄	194.1	-0.4	193.7	

The solution exhibited mutarotation ; the initial values $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5461}} = 852.0^\circ$ and $[\alpha]_{\text{Hg}_{5780}} = 294.8^\circ$ changing to 340.7° and 284.8° respectively in course of 4 hours.

TABLE XII.

Benzylaminomethylenecamphor.

solvent.	conc. g/100 c.c.	<i>d</i> or <i>l</i> .	H _g ⁵⁴⁶¹ .	H _g ⁵⁷⁸⁶ .
Chloroform	0.4032	<i>d</i>	+339.9°	+279.1*
	0.4000	<i>l</i>	-340.0	-278.8
Methyl alcohol	0.4020	<i>d</i>	+365.7	+307.3
	0.4060	<i>l</i>	-364.6	-307.9
Benzene	0.4052	<i>d</i>	+297.4	+245.6
	0.4004	<i>l</i>	-297.2	-244.8

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